

Effect of boron on second phases (σ) and mechanical properties in stainless steel S31254 after solution treatment

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Abstract: The effect of boron content on the microstructures and mechanical properties of S31254 precipitates were studied after heat treatments. The time and temperature of second phase (σ) of S 31254 solution under different solid solution time and temperature were obtained. The results show that with the boron content in steel is 0.002 %, affected positively and decreased the formation of second phases (σ) significantly. The solid solution temperature of precipitation phase is 1200°C, and the relatively pure austenite structure can be obtained after 4 hours of solution treatment. The second phase (σ) precipitated in and outside the grain boundaries has been re-solidified into the matrix during the hot working process. In the solution treatment, the second phase in the grain boundary dissolves gradually with the time increases. Hardness and UTS both were found higher in S31254-2 samples solid solution at 1200 °C for 1 and 4 hours.

Keywords: solution treatment, super austenite stainless steel, second phase, boron, mechanical properties

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Accepted: 19 November, 2022; **Published:** 07 December, 2022

How to cite this article: Sikander Sharif, Yasir Hashmi, Muhammad Saqlain Qurashi, Burhan Hashmi, Sania Hanif (2022). Effect of boron on second phases (σ) and mechanical properties in stainless steel S31254 after solution treatment. *North American Academic Research*, 5(11), 164-177. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7411226>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

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Introduction

As a stainless steel with special properties, super austenitic stainless steel is a high corrosion resistant stainless steel containing high chromium and high molybdenum. It can maintain good corrosion resistance even in high temperature, seawater and other harsh environments. In some cases, it can be compared with Hastelloy and titanium plate. It is a high economic stainless steel with high corrosion resistance. However, in the process of industrial production, because the material is formed at high temperature and the cooling speed is slow, a large number of σ Phase [1]. The results

show that even after solution treatment at 1180 °C, there are still a lot of residues in the material σ Phase, which reduces the corrosion resistance and mechanical properties of the material [2,3].

Many studies have been carried out at home and abroad on the aging precipitation behavior of super austenitic stainless steel and s31254 stainless steel [4-8]. The results show that s31254 super austenitic stainless steel will have a large number of second phase precipitation at 850 °C, which is mainly caused by σ Intermetallics rich in Cr, Mo and low Ni. These precipitates are mainly massive and acicular in shape, mainly distributed in grain boundaries and crystals, and some of them will appear in twins. With the prolongation of aging time, the precipitates gradually grow and increase in quantity, and their Cr and Mo contents gradually increase, while the Ni content gradually decreases; During the aging treatment at 900 °C, the precipitates formed preferentially on the grain boundary. With the extension of aging time, the number and size of precipitates gradually increased, and finally formed a network distribution on the grain boundary; TEM and EDS characterization confirmed that the precipitates were rich in Cr, Mo and low Ni.

Although many scholars at home and abroad have carried out a detailed study on the aging precipitation behavior of the precipitates in super austenitic stainless steel, there are few studies on the solid solution behavior of the precipitates in s31254 by the solid solution treatment process, especially on the effect of boron addition on the solid solution behavior of the precipitates in the material. The solid solution process adopted by these scholars in the research process is carried out according to relevant standards, but in fact, the complete austenite structure can not be obtained by using this solid solution system, and a small amount of unsolved second phase is still left in the structure, which will reduce the corrosion resistance and toughness of the material. In addition, there are many studies on the influence of B on the properties of stainless steel and other materials at home and abroad [9-19], but there are few studies on the solid solution behavior. Therefore, the key research direction of this paper is to get the appropriate solution treatment process and how the second phase of the solution process is solved. This paper focuses on the effect of Boron on the second phase dissolution behavior of s31254 in the solid solution process, in order to clarify the effect of Boron on its solid solution law and provide support for the production and application of materials.

Research Methodology

Material preparation

Sample preparation

Two heats of s31254 stainless steel are smelted in 50kg vacuum induction furnace, one of which is numbered s31254-1 without adding boron; Add 0.002% boron to the other furnace, numbered s31254-2; The main chemical components are shown in Table 1. It can be seen from the table that s31254 used in the test meets the standard requirements in ASTM A312. The ingot is heated to 1250 °C in the furnace at room temperature for 40 min. The ingots are hot rolled into 14 mm thick plates by a four high mill and the material is then cut into 14 × fourteen × 3 mm specimen and solution treated at different temperatures.

Table 1 Chemical component of S31254 (mass fraction /%)

Sr#	C	Si	Mn	P	S	Cr	Ni	Mo	Cu	N	B
S31254-1	0.010	0.610	0.430	0.024	0.001	20.180	18.000	6.000	0.690	0.193	0.000
S31254-2	0.015	0.580	0.910	0.015	0.004	20.000	18.070	6.170	0.800	0.210	0.002

Experimental method

The two kinds of s31254 stainless steel after cutting were treated by resistance heating furnace at 1180 °C, 1200 °C and 1220 °C for 1 h, 2 h and 4 h respectively, and then rapidly cooled to room temperature. After inlaying, rough grinding,

fine grinding and polishing, the samples after the test are corroded with aqua regia solution (the ratio of concentrated hydrochloric acid to concentrated nitric acid is 3:1). Observe the microstructure with Leica DMR type metallographic microscope, analyze the microstructure and precipitation of the sample after the solid solution test with leo438vp type scanning electron microscope, conduct element analysis on the precipitated phase with Kevex spectrometer, and characterize the microstructure of the sample with high-resolution transmission electron microscope, so as to obtain the influence of solid solution time, temperature and boron content on the second phase solid solution.

For the evaluation of mechanical properties, tensile specimens were cut via a water cooled line cutting CNC machine (EDM Wire Cut 7740) under the parameters of ASTM standard E8 from the ingots of each alloy after following the standard heat treatment procedure. Dog-bone shaped tensile specimens with a gauge length of 7 mm, thickness and width of 1.2 mm, were tested at room temperature after being polished with 2000-grit SiC papers. Tensile tests were conducted by means of a universal testing machine (UTM 5105 electronic universal tester-50 Ton) at the strain rate of 1.5 mm/min. The yield strengths of all the tensile specimens were calculated using 0.2% offset method. Parameters for hardness tests were 10mm diameter carbide ball indenter and with the load of 300g for 20 seconds indented. Sample size for hardness were kept 10×10×3 mm.

Test process and result discussion

Microstructure analysis of sample s31254-1 super austenitic stainless steel after solution treatment

Figure 1 shows the microstructure of the sample before solution treatment. It can be seen that the microstructure is composed of austenite and precipitates, which are mainly concentrated in the area with large deformation and are connected into a network along the grain boundary.

Fig. 1: Microstructure of samples S31254-1 before solution treatment

The main reason for solution treatment of sample S31254-1 at 1180 °C is that it precipitates during deformation. The phase is very stable and may be dissolved only at a higher heat treatment temperature (above about 1170 °C), while the American national standard ASTM A480 clearly points out that the solid solution temperature is 1150 °C. Therefore, 1180 °C is selected as the starting temperature of the solid solution in this test.

Fig. 2: Microstructure of samples S31254-1 after solution treatment at 1180 °C:
(a) 0 h, (b) 1h, (c) 2 h, (d) 4 h

Fig. 2 shows the microstructure of sample s31254-1 after solution treatment at 1180 °C for different times. It can be seen that the microstructure is composed of austenite and precipitated phase. It can be seen from Fig. 2 (b) that there are still a large number of precipitates in the structure of the sample without boron added 1h after solid solution, especially in the local area with large deformation. The main reason is that during solidification of the original slab, the composition segregation [2,7] causes the second phase to gather in the local area with large deformation. Due to the insufficient solid solution temperature and short time, the precipitates cannot be completely dissolved. Figure 2 (a) shows the structure in the initial state of solid solution. From the figure, it can be seen that in addition to the dense appearance of precipitates at the grain boundary, some precipitates appear in an obvious chain shape through multiple grains, which is the trace of local precipitate accumulation caused by component segregation during solidification of the original slab and retained after deformation. Especially in the case of high molybdenum content, the dissolution of precipitates needs higher temperature and longer time. With the extension of the solid solution time, the segregated elements gradually diffuse, the precipitated phases can be further dissolved, the precipitated phases that originally gathered into clusters gradually decompose, and only the original distribution traces of precipitated phases can be seen in local areas; At the same time, a large number of precipitates are dissolved at the grain boundary, and there are still a few precipitates in the original aggregation region, intragranular and grain boundary. Fig. 2 (d) shows that when the solid solution time reaches 4h, the original precipitated phase has basically dissolved, no precipitated phase can be seen in the crystal, and only a few residual precipitated phases can be seen at the grain boundary.

Fig. 3: Microstructure of samples S31254-1 after solution treatment at 1200 °C:
(a) 0 h, (b) 1h, (c) 2 h, (d) 4 h

Fig. 3 shows the microstructure of sample s31254-1 after solution treatment at 1200 °C. It can be seen that the microstructure is composed of austenite and different amounts of precipitates. When the solid solution temperature is increased to 1200 °C, the dissolution rate of the precipitates increases obviously. Compared with 1180 °C, a large number of precipitates have been dissolved after aging for 1 h, and the dissolution rate has increased significantly; When the aging time reaches 2 h, only the precipitates in the area with large deformation are not completely dissolved, and the precipitates in the original segregation zone change from cluster distribution to intermittent distribution. Although there are still large precipitates at the grain boundary, their aggregation degree and size are much smaller than those in the original state; In particular, no precipitates can be seen after 4 h, but the grain growth is obvious at this time, and its microstructure is shown in Fig. 3 (d).

Fig. 4 shows the microstructure of sample s31254-1 after solution treatment at 1220 °C. It can be seen that the microstructure is also composed of austenite and different amounts of precipitates. When the solid solution temperature is increased to 1220 °C, it can be seen from Figure 4 that the dissolution rate of the second phase continues to accelerate, but the increase in the dissolution rate within 1 h is not particularly obvious, and there is still an obvious second phase in some parts. At this time, the dissolution of the second phase is gradually dissolved in the crystal, while the dissolution rate of the precipitated phase with large particles at the grain boundary is slow. Although the solution time is prolonged and the austenite grains grow, the second phase is still not completely dissolved in the original accumulation area of the second phase after solution treatment, and the trace or orientation of the original rolling deformation is still maintained from the perspective of its existing form. Even after solution treatment at 1220 °C for 2 h, there is still an undissolved second phase, which is due to the slow dissolution rate of the original large particle second phase at the grain boundary. This is also the reason why the granular second phase appears in the crystal. When the solid solution time reaches 4 h, the microstructure is a single austenite structure, and almost no precipitates can be seen.

Fig. 4: Microstructure of samples S31254-1 after solution treatment at 1220 °C:
(a) 0 h, (b) 1 h, (c) 2 h, (d) 4 h

3.2 microstructure analysis of sample s31254-2 super austenitic stainless steel after solution treatment

Fig. 5: Microstructure of samples S31254-2 before solution treatment

Sample s31254-2 was also treated at 1180 °C, 1200 °C and 1220 °C for different times. Figure 5 (a) shows the microstructure of sample s31254-2 before solution treatment. It can be seen that the microstructure is composed of austenite and precipitated phase. Compared with s31254-1 (Figure 1), the precipitated same samples gather along the area with large deformation, but their quantity, size and degree of aggregation are significantly weakened.

Fig. 6 shows the microstructure of sample s31254-2 after solution treatment at 1180 °C. It can be seen that the microstructure is composed of austenite and different amounts of precipitates. It can be seen from Fig. 6 that it is difficult to dissolve the second phase at 1180 °C. After 2 hours of solid solution, the second phase has been significantly reduced, there are still some small undissolved second phases in the matrix, and the second phase at the grain boundary is also gradually reduced. Its dissolution characteristics are different from the dissolution process of s31254-1 sample. Compared with s31254-1 sample, the precipitated phase of the sample after adding boron is more dispersed. When the solid solution time is extended to 4 h, the precipitates still exist along the grain boundary, but the precipitates have become fine and intermittently distributed. Compared with s31254-1 sample without boron, the precipitates in super austenitic stainless steel containing boron are easier to re dissolve into the austenitic matrix and obtain nearly complete solid solution austenite structure.

Therefore, the addition of 0.002% boron can promote the solid solution of the second phase. This is mainly because the segregation of boron at the grain boundary increases the diffusion ability of elements, which also promotes the dissolution of the second phase. However, the improvement of the solubility of the second phase by 0.002% boron is not very obvious. For the second phase in the aggregation region, boron can significantly increase its dissolution rate, but this effect is not obvious in the segregation region.

Fig. 6: Microstructure of samples S31254-2 after solution treatment at 1180 °C:
(a) 0 h, (b) 1 h, (c) 2 h, (d) 4 h

Fig. 7 shows the microstructure of sample s31254-2 after solid solution treatment at 1200 °C. It can be seen from the figure that the second phase of this temperature line dissolves faster. Only after solid solution for 1h, the second phase has been significantly reduced. Compared with sample s31254-1 under the same conditions, there are relatively fewer insoluble second phases in the matrix. The second phase on the grain boundary has been basically invisible, only there are fine point precipitates in the crystal. When the solid solution time is 2h, the precipitates in the matrix are basically re dissolved, and only a small part of undissolved precipitates exist on a few grain boundaries. When the solid solution time was extended to 4h, no precipitates were found in the grains and grain boundaries, but the grains grew. After adding 0.002% boron, the dissolution rate of the second phase in the material increases obviously. The main reasons are as follows: first, the increase of temperature increases the diffusion ability of elements and promotes the dissolution of the second phase, which can be well proved by the solid solution process of sample s31254-1; Second, the addition of boron will have a certain impact on the distribution behavior of molybdenum, and also affect the stability of the second phase. Adding a certain amount of boron makes the precipitation temperature of the second phase drop significantly, and the pure austenite structure can be obtained by solid solution at a lower temperature.

Fig. 7: Microstructure of samples S31254-2 after solution treatment at 1200 °C:
 (a) 0 h, (b) 1 h, (c) 2 h, (d) 4 h

Fig. 8 shows the microstructure of sample s31254-b-20 after solid solution treatment at 1220 °C. It can be seen that the dissolution rate of the second phase continues to accelerate at 1220 °C. At 1h of solid solution, there are few second phases in the structure. Compared with sample s3254-1 under the same conditions, there are fewer insoluble second phases in the matrix. The second phase on the grain boundary has been completely dissolved, and there are a small amount of fine precipitates in the crystal. When the solid solution time is 2H or 4h, the precipitates in the matrix have been completely re dissolved, and only a small part of undissolved precipitates are found on the grain boundaries of the samples with solid solution time of 2H. When the solid solution time is extended to 4h, the precipitates in the crystal and at the grain boundary have been completely dissolved, but the grains have grown.

Fig. 8: Microstructure of samples S31254-2 after solution treatment at 1220 °C:
 (a) 0 h, (b) 1 h, (c) 2 h, (d) 4 h

3.3 analysis on the influence mechanism of Boron on the back dissolution of precipitates in super austenitic stainless steel during solid solution treatment

The results show that the dissolution temperature of the second phase in super austenitic stainless steel s31254 decreases greatly after adding boron, which indicates that boron can promote the dissolution of the second phase at the same solid solution temperature. The dissolution rate of the second phase in the sample without boron is very slow. On the one hand, it is related to the number of the original second phase in the structure, on the other hand, it is also related to the size of the precipitated second phase in the grain boundary region.

Fig. 9: Microstructure of samples S31254-1 after solid solution at 1200°C for 40 min:

(a) 200 X, (b) 500 X, (c) 2000 X

Figure 9 shows the microstructure of s31254-1 sample after solid solution at 1200 °C for 40 min. it can be seen from the figure that the second phase of the sample without boron can not be fully dissolved even after solid solution treatment, and there is still an obvious large-size skeletal second phase among the grains. This kind of second phase is formed during processing. Due to element segregation, the growth mechanism of the second phase is different from that of the independent phase. In the process of element enrichment, the second phase is preferentially formed, and then the adjacent second phase is formed through element segregation. Because element enrichment takes a certain time, the skeletal second phase is formed with the continuous enrichment of elements. The effect of this kind on the solid solution process is very obvious, and it can be dissolved only after a long time of solid solution at 1220 °C. However, for the sample with boron added, the dissolution rate is very fast, and it can be basically dissolved at 1220 °C in only 1 h. Comparing the dissolution of the second phase under different solid solution conditions, it can be seen that the composition of the second phase has no obvious change, and they all belong to the same kind of precipitates.

Fig. 10: Microstructure of S31254 with different boron content after solution treatment at 1180 °C for 4h: (a) S31254-1, (b) S31254-2

Figure 10 shows the microstructure of s31254 with and without boron after solid solution at 1180 °C for 4 hours. It can be seen from Figure 10 that at 1180 °C, there are still many undissolved precipitates in the sample without boron after

solid solution for 4 hours; However, the second phase in the sample with boron was almost invisible. The results show that the sample with boron can dissolve the second phase at a lower temperature.

Fig. 11: Microstructure of S31254 with different boron content after solution treatment at 1200 °C for 4 h: (a) S31254-1, (b) S31254-2

Fig. 12: Microstructure of S31254 with different boron content after solution treatment at 1220 °C for 4 h: (a) S31254-1, (b) S31254-2

After solution treatment at 1200 °C and 1220 °C for 4 hours, it can be seen from figures 2-11 and 2-12 that the grain growth of the sample without boron is very slow, while the grain growth of the sample with boron is faster.

3.4 composition analysis of precipitates in super austenitic stainless steel

Fig. 13 is the energy spectrum after 1 h solution treatment at 1200 °C. In comparison, the precipitated phase after boron addition is obviously improved. The results of energy spectrum and electron probe microanalysis show that the samples containing boron σ The content of Mo in the second phase is 10.88%, which is lower than 18.04% of the sample without boron, that is, adding boron can reduce the content of Mo in the second phase; This also shows that the content of Mo in the second phase of the boron added sample decreases during the re dissolution, which is conducive to the rapid dissolution of the second phase.

Fig. 13: EDS analysis of microstructure of S31254 with different boron content after solution treatment at 1220 °C for 1 h: (a) S31254-1, (b) S31254-2

In the process of solid solution σ Mechanism analysis of phase back dissolution

The dissolution of the second phase starts from the initial larger size and belongs to element redistribution. After adding boron, the dissolution rate of the second phase increases obviously, and the second phase gradually dissolves from block to needle and dot, and finally completely dissolves. In the process of solid solution for materials without boron, the skeletal second phase gradually dissolves at first, and breaks first in the length direction to form chain precipitates. With the extension of solid solution time, the fine second phase is dissolved first, and the massive second phase appears in local positions in the structure. Finally, the massive second phase is gradually dissolved. At this time, the dissolution law of the second phase is the same as that of boron, but the time is significantly longer than that of the latter.

Through the above experiments, it is found that adding boron makes σ The dissolution rate of the phase is accelerated. The fundamental factor affecting the diffusion rate is the diffusion activation energy. In the dissolution process of the second phase, when the dissolution rate is controlled by diffusion, the dissolution of the precipitated phase involves two processes: the transfer and separation of atoms at the phase interface, the matrix and precipitation (interfacial diffusion), and the diffusion of solutes outside the interface (long-distance diffusion). The initial shape of the second phase has a fundamental influence on the overall diffusion process due to the different diffusion velocities of the atoms in the matrix and the second phase. At the same time, the dissolution rate also has a great relationship with the initial distribution of the second phase. Compared with the initial distribution of the second phase, the spatial distribution of the second phase produced in the precipitation process has a relatively small effect on the precipitation dissolution.

5. Mechanical properties

After solid solution at 1200 °C for 1 and 4 hours, mechanical properties were checked with the parameters described in the section of experimental. More than 10 locations were tested for hardness as shown in figure 14. Sample solid solution at 1200 °C for 1h give properties as: average 199.05 HV hardness were observed in S31254-2 sample and but S31254-1 sample 193.68HV. Less hardness is shown by sample S31254-1 which is without boron. Which means boron become the reason for hardness increment. And sample solid solution 1200 °C for 4h were observed with 203.05 HV (S31254-2) and 191.75HV (S31254-1).

Fig. 14: Vickers Hardness tests of both S31254-1 and S31254-2 steels (a) 1200 °C for 1 hour solid solution and (b) 1200 °C for 4 hours solid solution

Samples solid solution at 1200 °C for 1 and 4 hours then tested for stress and strain curves as shown in figure 15. Sample S31254-2 solid solution for 1 hour showed 683.45 MPa higher UTS (ultimate tensile strength) than S31254-1 which showed 673.56 MPa UTS. Sample S31254-2 heat treated for 2 hours showed UTS 739.55 MPa but sample without boron S31254-1 showed 723.85 MPa, which is 15Mpa less.

Fig. 15: Stress strain curves of both S31254-1 and S31254-2 steels (a) 1200 °C for 1 hour solid solution and (b) 1200 °C for 4 hours solid solution

Conclusion

In this paper, the microstructure evolution of s31254 samples with and without boron was compared and analyzed after solution treatment at 1180 °C, 1200 °C and 1220 °C for different time (1H, 2h and 4h). It can be seen that boron content has an obvious effect on the back dissolution of precipitated phase. The specific research results are as follows:

- (1) S31254 sample is made by σ Composition of precipitates and austenite: the Mo content of precipitates in s31254-1 sample is significantly higher than that in s31254-2, and σ The number and size of the phases are large and mainly concentrated at the grain boundary.
- (2) The dissolution rate of precipitates in s31254-2 sample is significantly faster than that in s31254-1 sample. At the same time, boron can also reduce the dissolution temperature of precipitates in super austenitic stainless steel, that is, at a lower temperature, all precipitates can be dissolved back into the austenitic matrix.
- (3) Hardness and UTS both were found higher in S31254-2 samples solid solution at 1200 °C for 1 and 4 hours.

Acknowledgments: I thankful to my my supervisor, my serniors espically Muhammad Saqlain Qurashi (PhD), who really guided me and supervised me during this research.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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